

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract. *Critical thinking is a complex cognitive process that involves the ability to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information beyond the parameters of given arguments or conditions. Critical thinking also entails the ability to critically evaluate viewpoints, justifications, or claims to identify potential biases that may influence the reasoning presented. Given the significance of critical thinking and its relevance to foreign language teaching, further research on the topic is highly recommended.*

Аннотация. *Критическое мышление - это сложный когнитивный процесс, включающий в себя способность анализировать, оценивать и синтезировать информацию за пределами параметров заданных аргументов или условий. Критическое мышление также подразумевает способность критически оценивать точки зрения, обоснования или утверждения, чтобы выявить потенциальные предубеждения, которые могут влиять на представленные рассуждения. Учитывая важность критического мышления и его актуальность для преподавания иностранных языков, настоятельно рекомендуется проводить дальнейшие исследования по этой теме.*

Annotatsiya. *Tanqidiy fikrlash - bu berilgan dalillar yoki shartlar doirasidan tashqarida ma'lumotni tahlil qilish, baholash va umumlashtirish qobiliyatini o'z ichiga olgan murakkab kognitiv jarayon hisoblanadi. Tanqidiy fikrlash, shuningdek, xulosa chiqarishda ta'sir qiluvchi potentsial tarafkashliklarni aniqlash uchun nuqtai nazarlarni, asoslarni yoki da'volarni tanqidiy baholash qobiliyatini o'z ichiga oladi. Tanqidiy fikrlashning ahamiyati va chet tillarni o'qitish bilan bog'liqligi sababli, ushbu mavzu bo'yicha qo'shimcha tadqiqot ishlarini olib borish juda tavsiya etiladi.*

Keywords: *critical thinking, analysis, evaluation, inference, explanation, self-regulation, problem-solving, creativity, FLT*

Ключевые слова: *критическое мышление, анализ, оценка, вывод, объяснение, саморегуляция, решение проблем, креативность, FLT*

Kalit so'zlar: *tanqidiy fikrlash, tahlil qilish, baholash, xulosa chiqarish, tushuntirish, o'z-o'zini tartibga solish, muammoni hal qilish, ijodkorlik, FLT*

The concept of critical thinking. The rapidly revolutionizing era involves possessing an ability that enables the individual to synthesize data, resolve problematical issues and adjust to ever-changing surroundings. This prominent ability is named as critical thinking. 'Critical thinking is the art of analyzing and evaluating

thinking with a view to improving it’(Paul, Elder 2008) Yet, it doesn’t mean that critical thinking is solely grounded on analysis or evaluation. ‘Critical thinking is the ability to think clearly and rationally about what to do or believe’(Elder, Paul 2010) It can call for action by enhancing reasoning and improving decision-making processes.

The key components of critical thinking

To draw a clear conceptual picture of critical thinking, the encompassed key components need to be identified in details. The first crucial element in critical thinking is believed to be analysis which is the ability to single out arguments, claims and underlying assumptions in the given content in the aim of achieving a clear understanding. Next essential constituent of critical thinking is considered to be evaluation which can enable learners to assess the credibility of sources, the relevance of information and the validity of evidence. Inference is also a useful segment of critical thinking to be able to draw logical conclusions based on reasoning by making connections between ideas. When a piece of information is well understood, evaluated and reasoned, it is time to clearly articulate, justify and support one’s explanation that’s the fourth fragment of critical thinking. Another major part is self-regulation which facilitates reflection on thoughts. Critical thinking also comprises problem-solving and creativity which can definitely communicate with complex situations by approaching from multiple different angles.

Analysis	Dividing intricate data into manageable chunks for improved comprehension. This entails recognizing claims, arguments, and the presumptions that underlie them
Evaluation	Determining the reliability and applicability of data sources. This entails challenging reliability of the data offered and taking into account other points of view.
Inference	Using reasoning and the evidence at hand to arrive at logical conclusions. It necessitates identifying trends and relating concepts.
Explanation	Clearly stating line of reasoning and providing evidence and logical arguments to back one’s conclusions.
Self-regulation	Examining one's own values, beliefs, prejudices, and mental processes to make sure they support reasonable arguments.
Problem-solving	Using critical thinking techniques to find answers to challenging issues by taking into account various viewpoints and possible results.
Creativity	Using creative thinking to come up with new ideas or tackle challenges from many perspectives.

The significance of critical thinking in FLL

As a higher-order cognitive skill, the importance of critical thinking needs to be stressed exclusively in the context of foreign language learning since acquiring a new

language demands not only a good knowledge of language aspects including grammar and vocabulary, but also a mastery of applying obtained skills in complex communicative real-life contexts. To cultivate this, learners need to be turned into an active learner rather than kept as a passive recipient of input by encouraging them to question unproven assumptions for the sake of clarity in order to foster a mindset that is avid for constant development. When it's effectively tailored, learners can comprehend the complexities of cross-cultural communication and establish meaningful interactions by contributing to discussions in a wide range of personal and professional settings.

Critical thinking development framework. To achieve the desired benefits of critical thinking in foreign language learning, comprehensively developing steps need to be taken both inside and outside of the classroom environment. Firstly, knowledge needs to be constructed in an appropriate way so that it leads to active implementation and brand new concepts regeneration. It requires to discern what information is missing and to identify what gaps need to be filled. Acknowledging possible deficiencies in one's own understanding may take the form of posing questions to prompt further investigation and enquiry (Ennis, 2018). Once shortcomings are discovered and research questions are postulated, it is time to discriminate amongst information by distinguishing fact from opinion, evidence from assumption and as a result acquire requisite realization. It can be successfully attained as long as conceptual relationships are constructed between existing knowledge structures and newly developed inputs in an organized manner. Secondly, reasoning is of a high importance to be evaluated by applying logic, identifying motivations and justifying arguments in a given content. Reflective application of logic can be used to assess the validity or truth of a particular conclusion.

It can also be applied predictively (i.e. beyond the parameters of a given argument or set of conditions) in order to make sound predictions as to what an argument or set of conditions mean – or whether they are still valid – in a different context (Ong et al., 2018). It comprises the capacity to recognize errors and logical fallacies in a variety of reasoning representations. In addition to applying logic, critical thinking necessitates the capacity to recognize and appraise the implicit elements that influence one's own or another's reasoning. Related to this, it involves having the ability to critically evaluate viewpoints, justifications, or claims stated in order to spot potential biases that might be influencing the logic put out.

Thirdly, analytical and evaluative decision-making is necessarily required to constitute an ideal outcome. To make an effective decision, one first needs to understand the problem or situation about which a decision needs to be made, in order to derive criteria for judging the decision (Ennis, 1985; Moore, 2010). It involves

assessing how well certain options will satisfy the demands of a given challenge or problem while still operating within the conditions or constraints imposed by the situation (Jimenez-Alexandre & Puig, 2012).

Considering the importance of critical thinking and the necessity of developing the skill in foreign language teaching, to conduct further research works on the topic is highly recommended.

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